

PRAGMATICITY OF RELIGIOUS TEXTS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Resume: In recent years, there has been a noticeable increase in interest in the problems of religious (sacred) language, religious communication, and religious discourse in linguistics. The author of this article seeks to show that the content of religious texts is multifaceted and multidimensional, and therefore the study of the language of confessional texts should be carried out comprehensively, in particular, taking into account the role and place of a particular text in confessional culture and in the history of religion.

Keywords: semantic and pragmalinguistic analysis of a religious text, language, Turkic vocabulary, pragmatics.

Contacting of languages and cultures in the republics of Central Asia (in the CIS) has an ancient history. In this multi-ethnic, poly- linguistic geographic space, their "collision" and contact co -functioning with the manifestation of donation and recipient is a common occurrence. This contact with Farsi, with Arabic, with Mongolian, with Russian, led to serious mutual enrichment of languages, cultures and peoples.

Each era of contact between languages and cultures of different ethnic groups leaves its mark on their development and improvement, which is realized, first of all, in language and culture. At the same time, the national language, as a rule, remains the same national as it was, but with borrowings from the contacting languages, for example: Arabic, Persian, Russian vocabulary in the Turkic languages.

At present, the English language is actively entering the Turkic world of Eurasia, penetrating almost all social aspects of the activity of the individual and society. The entry of the English language is carried out systematically, at the state level. This is explained by the fact that through the English language, young people can enter a wider and deeper field of activity in many social spheres - educational, scientific, economic, diplomatic, etc.

Uzbek is a multi-dialect language. Its dialects are included in the system of three dialects of the Uzbek language - Karluk-Chigili , Kypchak, Oguz , which are also the main three dialects and Turkic languages in general. Thus, the Uzbek language is a language

consisting of dialects that differ sharply from each other, since some of them are formed in the system of one dialect, the second - in the system of another dialect, and the third - in the system of the third dialect. What unites the genetic Uzbek speakers of the Uzbek language is the normative Uzbek literary language, a language that sharply differs to the same extent from most dialects of the Uzbek language, especially Oguz and Kypchak.

A genetic speaker of the Uzbek language, as a rule, speaks the Uzbek native dialect and the native Uzbek literary language, i.e. he is an intralinguistic bilingual individual within his native language. This provision in the overwhelming majority also applies to the Uzbek territorial linguistic societies, striving to master the normative Uzbek literary language, which is carried out, first of all, in the school education system.

The term "pragmatics" was introduced by C. Maurice (from the Greek deed, action). Pragmatics studies the behavior of signs in real communication processes. The central concepts of pragmatics are context and speech act. The speech act is the core of the so-called Speech Act Theory (TRA). The theory of speech acts received an interesting development in the works of Grice, who developed the mechanisms of speech implication.

Pragmatics is an integral part of the study of speech, since, among other things, scientists pay attention to what external linguistic situation motivates the choice and use of certain linguistic means. In other words, in practical research, the main attention is paid to the communicative content of the utterance in different communication conditions.

Pragmatics, among other linguistic areas, is most associated with the problems of language use, since the use of language by a person is the main object of study of pragmatics. The concept of pragmatics has been and is being used to describe a fairly wide and heterogeneous spectrum of phenomena. This means that it is difficult to define the boundaries of pragmatics, but it is quite clear that pragmatics is related to areas of science dealing with communication problems.

The interdisciplinary nature of the initial concepts of linguopragmatics involves many factors, both proper linguistic, psychological, sociolinguistic, and socio-historical, national-cultural, ethnographic and other factors, into the circle of the problem of "man and language". All this led to the diversity of definitions of this area of linguistics.

The problems of linguoculturology and accent are analyzed in conjunction, since the culture of language and speech is closely related to the problem of speech accent; Decreasing the accent generally increases the cultural and linguocultural aspects of mastering a non-native language and vice versa.

The accent is seen as some kind of flaw in the speech in the second language and even as mistakes. This understanding of the accent in speech in the second language is widespread. In this case, the accent is a speech interference problem. With this approach to understanding the accent, one can both agree and disagree. We stand on the scientific position that accent is not fully speech interference: it is a phenomenon that is formed after overcoming speech interference at almost all levels of the language. Accent is an already well-established specificity of speech in a non-native language, which is not considered by many listeners and specialists as a disadvantage in speech in a second language. Such speech often attracts the attention of a large number of listeners, interlocutors. According to the definition in the Terminological Dictionary, an accent is "... a peculiar pronunciation in the Second Language, in which the Articulatory Base of the Mother Tongue is involuntarily manifested ...", further it is written that this is "... a manifestation of interference at the phonetic level."

In general, we agree with this definition of accent, but in particular, not completely. Firstly, in our opinion, it would be necessary to talk about some manifestation in speech in the second language of some features of the work (functions) of the articulation base of the native language, and not the entire work of the articulation base, because the individual and society speaking the second language, they already have a good or even perfect command of it (vocabulary, grammar, stylistics, prosody). The accent in this case manifests itself to a greater extent at the level of intonation, rhythm, tone, and then at the segmental phonemic - sound level, but which does not distort the sound -producing and acoustic norms of the second language. Therefore, the final part of the definition of accent in the dictionary as "... a manifestation of Interference at the phonetic level" (consonants - "at the sound level") can be attributed to the traditional everyday understanding of the accent. Accent is a phenomenon that is both typical and atypical, and manifests itself (or forms) after

overcoming speech interference, which is understood as obvious and implicit errors in speech in a second language, when such speech is perceived by specialists as lack of knowledge or poor, poor command of a non-native language, on which the individual is trying to communicate or which he is learning. Therefore, the understanding of the accent in speech, in our opinion, should be considered not as speech interference, but as a deviation that manifests itself in oral or written speech in the second language both intentionally (consciously) and involuntarily (unintentionally, unconsciously).

Let us give a simple example of the distortion of the meaning of the meaning of a sentence in the process of translation, while strictly observing the translation of individual words. According to the rule about word order in an English sentence, the center of the utterance, i.e. the new that is spoken of must be at the beginning. Therefore, translating the seemingly simple sentence "A man entered the church" is not so easy. You should think about what information is new: about a person or about the church into which he entered. Option "A man came into the church" means that the emphasis is on the person. This is new information for us and the word "man" is used with the indefinite article. If we already know about this person and we want to draw attention to the fact that he entered the church, the sentence should be translated "The man came into the church". The word "man" is used with the definite article. We cannot put the word "church" at the beginning of a sentence in English, since it acts as a circumstance (recall that declarative sentences in English can only begin with a subject).

Not all of these options are marked with confessional coloring. For example, for translation "Exaltation honest and life-giving Cross Lord's" offered not less four options: the Exaltation of the Holy and Living Cross, the Raising Up of the Honored and Live-giving Cross, the Feast of the Exaltation of the Holy Cross of Our Lord, the Elevation of the Live-creating Cross and So further. The choice of the optimal translation option remains with the researcher and depends on his experience, skills and desire to understand the issue.

When conducting a semantic and pragmalinguistic description of religious texts, one should not only take into account the peculiarities of their content and form, but also the social significance and features of functioning in a particular culture.

Literature:

1. Araeva L.A., Bulgakova O.A., Kalent'eva L.S. and others. Language picture of the world of Teleuts : monograph / otv. ed. A.V. Proskurin. - Kemerovo: KGU, 2016.
2. Gadomsky A.K., 2017, Religious language - theolinguistics - linguistics, Scientific notes of the Tauride State University. IN AND. Vernadsky, Philology Series, No. 20 (59), 1, p. 287–292.
3. Slyshkin G.G., 2000, From text to symbol: linguistic and cultural concepts of precedent texts in consciousness and discourse, Moscow: Academia .